

A REVIEW OF PAPERS ABOUT BIOCHEMISTRY OF CONTAMINATED SOILS FROM THE SCOPUS DATABASE PUBLISHED IN ENGLISH FOR THE PERIOD OF 2013-2022

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the analysis of various scientific works published on the topic of biochemical properties of contaminated soils in scientific publications indexed in the Scopus database between 2013 and 2022. The article analyzed 6,825 scientific works published in various scientific publications indexed in the Scopus database. The bibliographic analysis was carried out according to criteria such as the number of scientific works by publication years, authors, affiliation to countries and institutions, scientific journals and type of scientific works. The results of the analysis were depicted in graphs. As a result of the analysis, it was found that scientific works on the topic are unevenly distributed by countries, institutes, scientific journals and categories.*

Keywords: *authors, journals, article, review, biochemistry, contaminated soils, review, Scopus.*

Introduction

In the conditions of economic development in countries and increasing anthropogenic pressure studying changes in biochemical processes in soils contaminated with industrial and household wastes and other harmful substances is an urgent issue (1;2). Negative changes in the synthesis and activity of biologically active substances such as amino acids, enzymes and vitamins by plants and microorganisms are observed in polluted soils (3). As a result, biochemical processes occurring in the soil are disturbed (7). This leads to disruption of the nitrogen cycle in the soil, which is one of the main nutrients required for the growth and development of plants. That is, nitrogen fixation, assimilation, ammonification, nitrification and denitrification slow down. This, in turn, has a negative impact on the biogeochemical cycle. The relevance of studying the impact of pollution with harmful substances on biochemical processes in the soil is based on this.

Based on this, the study of biochemical changes in contaminated soils is under the constant attention of scientists, and scientific works on the subject are being published. But there is no bibliographic analysis of scientific works published in Scopus database on the topic of biochemical processes in contaminated soils. In this article, we aim to analyze the annual amount, authors, institutes, scientific journals and types of scientific works published in publications in the Scopus database in 2013-2022. According to the results of bibliographic analysis, it will be possible to draw a conclusion about the regional development of scientific works on this topic.

Materials and Methods

Based on the objective of the research, three subject areas selected from the Scopus database for the period of 2013-2022. Name of subject areas: 1. Environmental Science - 4741 papers 2. Agricultural and Biological Sciences – 1583 papers 3. Chemistry – 1182 papers, 4. Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology – 677, 5. Earth and Planetary Sciences - 1358. All

publications were analyzed and reviewed using biochemistry of contaminated soils as the keyword. Total of 6825 publications sorted out for the further analysis on biochemistry of contaminated soils issue. Then, a database was categorized including the year of publication, journal names, authors' names, countries, the type of publication and institutions. Figure 1 shows the flow of the selected methodology for the research.

Figure 1 Methodology flowchart for the research

Results and Discussion

Published papers on biochemistry of contaminated soils

The number of scientific works published by world scientists in the Scopus database on the biochemical properties of contaminated soils during the research period shows the relevance of the topic. 6825 scientific works were published in 2013-2022. Figure 2 shows the growth in the number of scientific papers published on the topic over the years. The number of scientific research papers on the topic increased by an additional 90 percent in 2022 compared to 2013.

Figure 2. Number of papers on biochemistry of contaminated soils by the year of publication in the world

Journals on biochemistry of contaminated soils

45 percent of the scientific works on the topic were published in 10 scientific journals presented in Figure 3. Scientific journals in the chart belong to EU countries and US publishers. Most of the scientific works have been published in scientific journals such as Science Of The Total Environment, Chemosphere, Environmental Pollution and Journal Of Hazardous Materials.

Figure 3. List of the journals on biochemistry of contaminated soils in the world

Top authors on biochemistry of contaminated soils

Authors play an important role in the analysis of a scientific topic. The number of scientists who studied the biochemical properties of contaminated soils and published their research results in scientific publications in the Scopus database during 2013-2022 was 3,200. Top 10 scientists by the number of scientific works on the topic (Fig. 3): R. Naidu (Australia), J. Rinklebe (Germany), A.L. Juhasz (Australia), L.Q. Ma (China), Y.S. Ok (South Korea), S. Ali (Pakistan), N. Bolan (Australia), B. Xing (China), M. Rizwan (Pakistan), C.A.M. Van Gestel (Nederland).

Figure 3. List of top authors published on biochemistry of contaminated soils issue in the world in 2013-2022 years

Top countries on biochemistry of contaminated soils

The problem of soil pollution with various wastes worries countries. It is important to study the impact of pollution caused by industrial and agricultural development on biochemical processes in soils. The scope of research depends on the depth of the problem in the country. Figure 4 shows data on the number of scientific works published in this direction in the countries. 36 percent of the total of 6,825 scientific works, i.e. 2,464, were written by Chinese scientists. In China, due to the development of industry, agriculture and strong demographic pressure, soil pollution has caused an increase in the number of scientific studies. Countries like USA (1082), India (633), Australia (409) and Germany (354) are in the next places. The first 10 countries include Great Britain, Spain, Pakistan, France and Italy. 94% of scientific works published in the 10 countries mentioned above. This means that the topic is under-researched in all countries.

Figure 4. List of top countries on biochemistry of contaminated soils issue in the world
Top institutions on biochemistry of contaminated soils

Based on the analysis of scientific works published in the Scopus database, world-leading institutions for studying the biochemical properties of contaminated soils were identified (Figure 5). All of the top 10 institutions are located in China. In 2013-2022, 30 percent of scientific works were published in these 10 universities.

Figure 5. List of top institutions on biochemistry of contaminated soils issue in the world
Publication type on biochemistry of contaminated soils

Scientific researchers publish the results in various types of scientific works. Over the last 10 years, the main part (5808, 85 percent) of 6825 scientific works devoted to the study of biochemical properties of contaminated soils are scientific articles (Fig. 6). It is followed by analytical materials (518, 8 percent) and conference abstracts (230, 3 percent). During the analyzed period, 32 (0.5 percent) books on the topic were published, and 68 (1 percent) books have chapters.

Figure 6. List of publication types on biochemistry of contaminated soils in the world
Conclusion

In the conditions of the development of industry and agriculture and the growing population of the world, the effective use of land resources and their protection are of great importance. Special attention should be paid to maintaining and increasing soil fertility. Studying the biochemical changes that occur in soils under the influence of pollution is important for their

protection. In this study, we analyzed the scientific works devoted to the study of the biochemical properties of contaminated soils published in the Scopus database from 2013 to 2022. The analysis focused on the number of scientific works published over the years, authors, institutions, journals and types of scientific works. As a result of the analysis, it was found that the number of published scientific works on the topic has increased over the years. China, the USA, India, Australia and a number of Western European countries are leading in conducting scientific research on the topic. The main part of the published scientific works corresponds to scientific articles, analytical reviews and conference proceedings.

In conclusion, scientific works dedicated to the study of biochemical processes in contaminated soils are not evenly distributed among countries and research institutes. In many developing industrial and agricultural countries, whose economic prosperity is directly dependent on agriculture, there is very little research on the subject. This may cause soil conservation problems in these countries. For this reason, it is necessary to pay special attention to the issues of financing research on the subject by research institutions and special funds operating in all countries.

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